

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example; 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Agronomic characteristics

Local indica rice varieties with desirable floral traits influencing outcrossing

H. C. Sarkar, plant breeder, and N. M. Miah, principal plant breeder, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

We sought to identify local indica rice varieties with desirable floral traits influencing outcrossing at BRRI main station, Joydebpur, during the 1982 transplanted aman season (Jul-Dec). Ninety-eight local varieties were grown in 5.4- × 2-m plots at 25- × 15-cm spacing using one seedling/hill. No fertilizer was applied.

Anther size (length), stigma size (length), and stigma exertion (%) were recorded for each entry. Anther length varied from 0.97 to 2.80 mm ($\bar{X} = 2.08 \pm 0.03$); stigma length from 0.42 to 1.34 mm ($\bar{X} = 0.85 \pm 0.02$); and stigma exser-

Varieties with larger anthers (≥ 2.00 mm long) and stigmata (≥ 1.00 mm long) with good exertion ($\geq 50\%$).

Variety	Anther length (mm)	Stigma length (mm)	Stigma exertion (%)
Ashwini	2.04	1.04	50
Kalagura	2.28	1.00	70
Lal Khama	2.08	1.04	60
Kumri	2.10	1.04	60
Loatung	2.10	1.06	75
Dhalai ropa	2.30	1.00	75
Holud jaron	2.14	1.00	70
Rajbhog	2.10	1.34	70
Kanpasha	2.18	1.14	80
Laida	2.48	1.08	75

tion from 0 to 90% ($\bar{X} = 46.24 \pm 2.58$).

Ten entries had larger anthers (≥ 2.00 mm) and stigmata (≥ 1.00 mm) with good exertion ($\geq 50\%$) (see table). The distribution of varieties by anther length, stigma length, and stigma exertion is shown in the figure. □

Varieties (no.)

Frequency distribution of varieties by anther length, stigma length, and stigma exertion.

Rice seed viability under two storage conditions

Md. Zahurul Haque and Mahmuda Haroon, Plant Physiology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

BR8 and BR9, two high yielding varieties (HYVs) recently released by BRRI for boro and aus seasons, yield better than

other HYVs, but field workers reported that germination percentage, particularly that of BR9, was poor. Rapid loss of seed viability was suspected to be a genetic trait.

We studied the seed viability range of BR8 and BR9, with BR3 as check. Boro-harvested seeds were sun-dried to 12% moisture (wet basis) and stored in metal baby food containers and in gunny bags